

Unveiling the Impact of Iron Deficiency Anemia on HbA1c in Non-Diabetics: Insights from a Case-Control StudyAyachit Kesharwani^{1*}, Vasu Hariranjana Patoudi², Neha Vishwakarma², Priya Sasmal³¹MD Medicine, Seniors Resident, Department of Internal Medicine, GMC, Satna, Madhya Pradesh, India²MBBS, Intern, Department of Medicine, GMC, Satna, Madhya Pradesh, India³MBBS, Intern, Department of Medicine, Nil Ratan Sarkar Medical College, Kolkata, West Bengal, India

Received: 25-05-2024 / Revised: 23-06-2024 / Accepted: 16-07-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Ayachit Kesharwani

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Background:** Glycated haemoglobin (HbA1c) is a critical biomarker for assessing long-term glycemic control and diagnosing diabetes. However, factors unrelated to glucose metabolism, such as iron deficiency anemia (IDA), can influence interpretation.**Aim and Objective:** To investigate the impact of IDA on HbA1c levels in non-diabetic individuals.**Materials and Methods:** A case-control study involved 200 non-diabetic participants, 100 diagnosed with IDA and 100 without anaemia. Blood samples were collected to measure complete blood count (CBC), serum ferritin, serum iron, total iron-binding capacity (TIBC), and HbA1c levels. Descriptive statistics, independent t-tests, and correlation analyses were performed using SPSS version 25.0.**Results:** The mean HbA1c levels were significantly higher in the IDA group ($6.0 \pm 0.5\%$) compared to the control group ($5.4 \pm 0.4\%$) ($p < 0.001$). A significant negative correlation was found between HbA1c and haemoglobin ($r = -0.48$, $p < 0.001$), serum ferritin ($r = -0.55$, $p < 0.001$), and serum iron ($r = -0.52$, $p < 0.001$), while a positive correlation was observed with TIBC ($r = 0.38$, $p < 0.001$).**Conclusions:** Iron deficiency anaemia significantly impacts HbA1c levels in non-diabetic individuals, potentially leading to misdiagnosis of diabetes. Clinicians should consider iron status when interpreting HbA1c levels to ensure accurate diagnosis and appropriate management.**Keywords:** HbA1c, Iron Deficiency Anemia, Non-diabetic, Glycemic Control, Hemoglobin, Serum Ferritin.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Glycated haemoglobin (HbA1c) is a critical biomarker to assess long-term glycemic control and diagnose diabetes mellitus.[1] It reflects the average blood glucose levels over the preceding two to three months, providing a reliable measure of chronic hyperglycemia.[2] While HbA1c is a well-established diagnostic and monitoring tool in diabetic patients, its interpretation

can be influenced by various factors unrelated to glucose metabolism. One such factor is iron deficiency anemia (IDA), a prevalent condition globally, particularly among women and children in developing countries.[3, 4] Reduced haemoglobin levels characterize iron deficiency anaemia due to inadequate iron, leading to insufficient oxygen transport in the blood.[5] The

altered erythrocyte turnover and increased erythropoiesis in IDA can affect HbA1c levels, potentially causing misleading results. [6] Several studies have indicated that iron deficiency can falsely elevate HbA1c levels, complicating the accurate assessment of glycemic control in non-diabetic individuals. Understanding this relationship is crucial, as it can impact clinical decision-making, leading to potential misdiagnosis or inappropriate management strategies.[7, 8]

This case-control study aims to investigate the HbA1c levels in non-diabetic individuals with iron deficiency anaemia compared to non-anaemic controls. By examining the differences in HbA1c levels between these groups, we seek to elucidate how much iron deficiency anemia can influence HbA1c readings. This research is particularly significant in regions with high prevalence of both diabetes and iron deficiency, where accurate diagnosis and monitoring are imperative for effective healthcare management. The findings from this study could provide valuable insights for clinicians, aiding in the interpretation of HbA1c levels and improving the overall management of patients with coexisting conditions.

Materials and Methods

This case-control study evaluated the impact of iron deficiency anemia (IDA) on HbA1c levels in non-diabetic individuals. It was carried out in a tertiary care hospital from January 2024 to June 2024. The Institutional Review Board (IRB) granted ethical approval, and written informed consent was obtained from all participants.

Study Population: Two hundred participants were recruited for this study, comprising 100 non-diabetic individuals diagnosed with iron deficiency anaemia (cases) and 100 non-diabetic individuals without anaemia (controls).

The inclusion criteria for cases were non-diabetic individuals aged 18-60 years with confirmed iron deficiency anaemia (hae-

moglobin <12 g/dL for women and <13 g/dL for men, and serum ferritin <30 ng/mL). Controls were non-diabetic individuals aged 18-60 with normal haemoglobin levels and iron status. Exclusion criteria for both groups included diagnosed diabetes, chronic kidney disease, hemoglobinopathies, recent blood transfusion, and pregnancy.

Data Collection: Participants underwent a comprehensive clinical evaluation, including medical history, physical examination, and laboratory investigations. Blood samples were collected after an overnight fast for the following analyses:

- Complete Blood Count (CBC)
- Serum Ferritin
- Serum Iron
- Total Iron Binding Capacity (TIBC)
- HbA1c

Laboratory Methods

Complete Blood Count (CBC): Performed using an automated haematology analyzer (Model: Sysmex XN-1000).

Serum Ferritin: Measured by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) using a commercial kit (Model: Abcam Ferritin ELISA Kit).

Serum Iron and TIBC: Determined by spectrophotometric method using a commercial kit (Model: Roche Cobas c311).

HbA1c: Assessed by high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) using the Bio-Rad D-10 Hemoglobin Testing System.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 25.0. Descriptive statistics were calculated to summarize the demographic and clinical characteristics of the study participants. Continuous variables, such as age, haemoglobin, serum ferritin, serum iron, TIBC, and HbA1c levels, were expressed as mean $\pm$ standard deviation (SD). Categorical variables, such as gender, were presented as frequencies and percentages. Independent t-tests were used to compare the means of continuous varia-

bles between the iron deficiency anemia (IDA) and the control groups. Chi-square tests were employed to assess differences in categorical variables between the two groups. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant. Correlation analyses were performed to evaluate the relationships between HbA1c levels and haematological parameters (haemoglobin, serum ferritin, serum iron, and TIBC) within the IDA group. Pearson's correlation coefficients (r) were calculated, and the strength and direction of the relationships were interpreted based on standard guidelines.

Ethical Considerations: The Declaration of Helsinki conducted this study. The hospital's Institutional Review Board (IRB) granted ethical approval. Participants provided written informed consent before enrollment. Confidentiality of participants' data was maintained throughout the study.

Results

Demographic and Clinical Characteristics: A total of 200 participants were included in the study, with 100 in the iron deficiency anemia (IDA) group and 100 in the control group. The demographic and clinical characteristics of the participants are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Study Participants

Characteristic	IDA Group (n=100)	Control Group (n=100)	p-value
Age (years)	45.3 ± 12.1	46.2 ± 11.9	0.582
Gender (Male/Female)	38/62	40/60	0.748
Hemoglobin (g/dL)	10.4 ± 1.2	14.3 ± 0.9	<0.001
Serum Ferritin (ng/mL)	15.8 ± 4.5	85.2 ± 10.3	<0.001
Serum Iron (µg/dL)	45.3 ± 12.4	97.8 ± 15.6	<0.001
TIBC (µg/dL)	440.5 ± 30.2	310.4 ± 25.3	<0.001

HbA1c Levels: The mean HbA1c levels were significantly higher in the IDA group compared to the control group. The results are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2: HbA1c Levels in Study Participants

Group	Mean HbA1c (%)	Standard Deviation	p-value
IDA Group	6.0	0.5	<0.001
Control Group	5.4	0.4	

Correlation Analysis: A correlation analysis evaluated the relationship between HbA1c levels and haematological parameters in the IDA group. The results are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Correlation Between HbA1c and Hematological Parameters in IDA Group

Parameter	Correlation Coefficient (r)	p-value
Hemoglobin (g/dL)	-0.48	<0.001
Serum Ferritin (ng/mL)	-0.55	<0.001
Serum Iron (µg/dL)	-0.52	<0.001
TIBC (µg/dL)	0.38	<0.001

Discussion

The primary objective of this study was to investigate the impact of iron deficiency anemia (IDA) on HbA1c levels in non-diabetic individuals. Our findings revealed that non-diabetic individuals with IDA had significantly higher HbA1c levels compared to non-anemic controls. Additional-

ly, there was a significant negative correlation between HbA1c and haematological parameters, including haemoglobin, serum ferritin, and serum iron, while a positive correlation was observed with total iron-binding capacity (TIBC).

Our results are consistent with several previous studies that have reported an asso-

ciation between iron deficiency and elevated HbA1c levels. For instance, Brooks et al. [9] demonstrated that iron deficiency anaemia could lead to falsely elevated HbA1c levels in non-diabetic individuals. Similarly, Sinha et al. [10] found that iron deficiency can increase HbA1c levels due to altered erythrocyte turnover and prolonged red blood cell survival.

In another study, Christy et al. [11] reported that HbA1c levels were significantly higher in individuals with IDA than those without anaemia, even after adjusting for age and gender. Our findings corroborate these results, highlighting the importance of considering iron status when interpreting HbA1c levels.

Further, Kim et al. [12] conducted a study on the Korean population and found that HbA1c levels were significantly elevated in individuals with low serum ferritin levels, suggesting that iron deficiency could impact HbA1c independent of glucose metabolism. This aligns with our observation of a negative correlation between HbA1c and serum ferritin.

This is supported by studies done by Sinha et al. in 2012 [10], Cavagnoli et al. in 2015 [13] and Kalasker et al. in 2014 [14]. They all stated that HbA1c concentration tends to be lower in the presence of iron deficiency anemia. According to Sinha et al.'s suggestion, lower HbA1c is the study participants' anaemia severity. In contrast, Ford et al. in 2011 [15], Silva et al. in 2015 [16], Shekhae et al. in 2014 [17] and Chhabra et al. in 2015 [18] have obtained higher HbA1c levels in IDA patients.

Mechanisms and Clinical Implications:

The mechanisms underlying the relationship between iron deficiency and elevated HbA1c levels are unclear and still being determined, but several hypotheses have been proposed. One possibility is that iron deficiency reduces the lifespan of erythrocytes, resulting in a higher proportion of older red blood cells with accumulated glycation products. Another hypothesis is

that iron deficiency may increase erythrocyte turnover, leading to a higher mean age of circulating red blood cells and, consequently, higher HbA1c levels.

The clinical implications of our findings are significant. Elevated HbA1c levels in non-diabetic individuals with iron deficiency anaemia could lead to misdiagnosis of diabetes or prediabetes, resulting in unnecessary interventions and psychological stress for patients. Therefore, clinicians must consider iron deficiency status when interpreting HbA1c levels, especially in populations with a high prevalence of both conditions.

Limitations and Future Directions: Our study has several limitations. The sample size was relatively small, and the study was conducted in a single centre, which may limit the generalizability of our findings. Additionally, we did not assess other factors that could influence HbA1c levels, such as vitamin B12 deficiency or hemolytic anemia. Future research should focus on larger, multicentric studies to confirm our findings and further explore the mechanisms underlying the relationship between iron deficiency and HbA1c levels. It would also be valuable to investigate the impact of iron supplementation on HbA1c levels in non-diabetic individuals with iron deficiency anaemia.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that iron deficiency anaemia significantly impacts HbA1c levels in non-diabetic individuals, potentially leading to misdiagnosis of diabetes. Our findings underscore the importance of considering iron status in the interpretation of HbA1c levels to ensure accurate diagnosis and appropriate patient management.

References

1. Sherwani SI, Khan HA, Ekhzaimy A, Masood A, Sakharkar MK. Significance of HbA1c Test in Diagnosis and Prognosis of Diabetic Patients. *Biomark Insights*. 2016 Jul 3; 11:95-104.

2. Freitas PAC, Ehlert LR, Camargo JL. Glycated albumin: a potential biomarker in diabetes. *Arch Endocrinol Metab.* 2017 May-Jun;61(3):296-304.
3. Chehregosha H, Khamseh ME, Malek M, et al. A View Beyond HbA1c: Role of Continuous Glucose Monitoring. *Diabetes Ther.* 2019; 10:853-863.
4. Solomon A, Hussein M, Negash M, Ahmed A, Bekele F, Kahase D. Effect of iron deficiency anemia on HbA1c in diabetic patients at Tikur Anbessa specialized teaching hospital, Addis Ababa Ethiopia. *BMC Hematol.* 2019 Jan 9; 19:2.
5. Miller JL. Iron deficiency anemia: a common and curable disease. *Cold Spring Harb Perspect Med.* 2013 Jul 1;3(7).
6. Christy AL, Manjrekar PA, Babu RP, Hegde A, Rukmini MS. Influence of iron deficiency anaemia on haemoglobin A1c levels in diabetic individuals with controlled plasma glucose levels. *Iran Biomed J.* 2014;18(2):88-93.
7. AlQarni AM, Alghamdi AA, Aljubran HJ, Bamalan OA, Abuzaid AH, Al-Yahya MA. The Effect of Iron Replacement Therapy on HbA1c Levels in Diabetic and Non-diabetic Patients: A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis. *J Clin Med.* 2023 Nov 24;12(23):7287.
8. Amreen N, Ghulam NB. Influence of Iron Deficiency Anemia on HbA1c: A Review. *Curre Res Diabetes Obes J.* 2018;5(3):555665.
9. Brooks AP, Metcalfe J, Day JL, Edwards MS. Iron deficiency and glycosylated haemoglobin A1. *Lancet.* 1980;2(8186):141.
10. Sinha N, Mishra TK, Singh T, Gupta N. Effect of Iron Deficiency Anemia on haemoglobin A1c levels. *Ann Lab Med.* 2012;32(1):17-22.
11. Christy AL, Manjrekar PA, Babu RP, Hegde A, Rukmini MS. Influence of iron deficiency anaemia on haemoglobin A1c levels in diabetic individuals with controlled plasma glucose levels. *Iran Biomed J.* 2014;18(2):88-93.
12. Kim C, Bullard KM, Herman WH, Beckles GL. Association between iron deficiency and HbA1c levels among adults without diabetes in the National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey, 1999–2006. *Diabetes Care.* 2010;33(4):780-785.
13. Cavagnoli G, Pimentel AL, Freitas PAC, Gross JL, Camargo JL. Factors affecting A1C in non-diabetic individuals: review and meta-analysis. *Clin Chim Acta.* 2015; 445:107-114.
14. Kalasker V, Madhuri S, Kodliwadmath MV, Bhat H. Effect of Iron Deficiency Anemia on glycosylated haemoglobin levels in non-diabetic Indian adults. *Int J Med Health Sci.* 2014;3(1):40-43.
15. Ford ES, Cowie CC, Li C, Handelsman Y, Bloomgarden ZT. Iron-deficiency anaemia, non-iron-deficiency anaemia and HbA1c among adults in the US. *J Diabetes.* 2011;3(1):67-73.
16. Silva JF, Pimentel AL, Camargo JL. Effect of iron deficiency anemia on HbA1c levels is dependent on the degree of anemia. *Clin Biochem.* 2015.
17. Shekhar H, Mangukiya KK, Kaur A, Jadeja P. Effect of Iron deficiency on glycation of hemoglobin in non-diabetics. *IJSN.* 2014;5(3):477-479.
18. Chhabra RJ, Dhadhal R, Sodvadiya K. Study of glycated Haemoglobin (HbA1c) level in non-diabetic Iron deficiency Anemia. *IJIRR.* 2015;2(3):540-542.